

An Approach to Encourage Girls' Protagonism in Exact Sciences and Engineering

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Abstract

The 21st century has come highlighting the world's concerns regarding competitiveness in face of new demands arising from accelerated technological advancement and, on the other hand, with inclusion, sustainability and quality of life. Therefore, gender equity in STEM fields has also become part of the goals of the 2030 agenda for sustainable development, with the aim of building a less exclusionary world. Faced with this urgent need to design a more inclusive future, several approaches have been proposed to attract girls to the exact sciences and engineering using active learning strategies and valuing the protagonism of these students in their school environment. In order to do so, a group of six ninth grade girls were invited to participate in the pilot project Accelerating Girls in Elementary School, conducted by undergraduate students in the exact sciences and engineering, and accompanied by professors from the school and from the University of Brasilia. In it, the Elementary School students were organized into a team to propose and present STEM hands-on practices, according to curricular contents, to their own class. The steps for designing such activities include weekly meetings for the development of the flipped classroom, quizzes and hands-on activities. Aspects and outcomes related to this process are described and discussed based on the literature, motivating reflections on strategies used to develop skills and competencies in STEM with young girls.

Keywords: Active Learning; Elementary School; Girls Protagonism; STEM Education.

1 Introduction

In recent years, the rapid technological development, on a worldwide scale, has been causing movements in education and in the job market in search of greater female inclusion, since women were historically placed on the margins of this academic and professional space. Despite advances, education is still not universal and as gender inequalities are still significant, and a current worry, not only the girls access to a current school, but also the limitations they face in the academic environment, more specifically, is reflected in the low number of girls regarding STEM education.

In line with current demands, the 2030 Agenda was conceived on September 2015 during the United Nations General Assembly. It is a document that encompasses objectives with a view to tackling global problems for the next 15 years (2016-2030), with these sustainable development objectives (SDGs) supported by three dimensions: social, environmental and economic. Among the 17 SDGs, two stand out, aiming at improvements in terms of quality education and gender equality, SDG4 and SDG5, respectively. In a report made in 2018, UNESCO — a United Nations agency specializing in education — places education in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) as one of the bases of the 2030 Agenda to achieve its goals, stressing that “ensuring that girls and women have equal access to STEM education and, ultimately, to STEM careers, is imperative for human rights, scientific and developmental perspectives” (UNESCO, 2018, p.15). Initiatives that take place at school, such as extracurricular activities, and joint projects with universities, have positive impacts on girls' interest in subjects and careers in the STEM field (Oliveira, Unbehaum, & Gava, 2019).

In view of this scenario, this study aims at reporting the activities developed by the Accelerating Girls project in Elementary School — an extension and research project from the University of Brasília developed in the scope of STEM education — reflecting on its reach and challenges in face of the promotion of female protagonism in areas of Exact Sciences and their technologies, especially with regard to their approach and execution with students from the public educational system of the Federal District, Brazil.

It should be noted that extension is one of the pillars of Brazilian federal institutions of higher education and comprises activities that aim to build paths to tackle social problems and issues, to popularize science, and to strengthen the interlocution with other knowledge, enhancing the interaction with teaching and research.

Given the context, the present research started from the need to identify more suitable strategies for the application of Active Learning Methodologies as an incentive and study motivation factor, and at the same time to stimulate the debate on the promotion of gender equality and empowerment of girls and women through STEM education.

The objective of this work is to present the aspects related to the development of STEM workshops in the ninth grade of a public elementary school and the learning gains of female elementary school students, monitors of this class, who participated in the development and execution of these workshops in the scope of a pilot proposal.

This is an action-research project in which proposals for the implementation of STEM workshops are carried out by the group of students and monitored during their realization. Reflections are made based on the results of the implementations and on interviews with the student monitors.

The work is organized as follows: the second section presents the bibliographic review that supports the measures adopted in the project; the third section exposes the context and model of the work conducted; the fourth section brings the partial results; and finally, the fifth section includes the concluding remarks of the developed research.

2 Active Learning and the Potential in Regard to Academic Protagonism

In the ideal future designed by the world nation, one of the main ideals is the respect for plurality and the appreciation of education in order to “ensure that all human beings can fulfill their potential in dignity and equality” (Agenda 2030, 2015, p. 1). It is common for each individual to have their particularities, so, in the field of education, it is natural that each student has preferences regarding the most effective study methods for themselves. Thus, seeking to respect students’ singularities, and make our education even more efficient, it is expected that as the ideal world is transformed into reality, new strategies and teaching-learning methods will be created and used.

Assuming that education is the main fuel for life improvements, it is important that the teaching-learning methods and strategies are able to promote the development of students' competencies and skills. Active learning strategies place the student in a more active role, contributing to the formation of responsible and critical citizens (Freire, 1997, p. 59). Placing the learner in a protagonist position means breaking away from the authoritarian model that reserves to the student the role of simply watching, listening and taking notes of pre-established contents (Felder & Brent, 2009). The report “The Future of Jobs” by the World Economic Forum (2020) points out some important and valued skills and competencies in the professional of the future. These skills and competences are: active learning, problem solving, critical thinking and analysis, creativity, originality and initiative; which are developed in activities such as debates, seminar presentations, experiments and workshop development.

These are knowledge sharing activities, and several tools can be used to make the process of intellectual gain more enjoyable. When the exchange is done horizontally, that is, by peers, it eliminates some obstacles that hinder learning. In this way, placing the learner as an active subject in the dissemination of knowledge encourages his peers to also feel part of this process.

In this dynamic, it is possible to work on communication strategies to promote the engagement of the parties involved, on research and study methods, on creativity in designing the presentation format of the content, and on skills with new active learning technologies. Thus, various aspects related to student empowerment, such as the responsibility to study and understand the subject before presenting the work, since she has the task of teaching the classmates, giving that student the right motivation to learn. Inverting the teacher-student role also affects the student's creativity when deciding which methods to use in order to make the presentation interesting, as he or she can create fun slides, search for videos, create quizzes, etc. In addition, it improves orality, argumentation and empathy, as Snider and Schnurer (2006) state in relation to debating activities.

There are several definitions and conceptions of active learning. Some definitions are presented by Mahlambi (2021):

According to Abu Bakar and Ismail (2020) and Jesionkowska et al. (2020), active learning is an action that directly involves learners in the process of learning. But Hartikainen et al. (2019:2-3) view active learning as “not just something that learners do independently but is somehow organised and monitored by an instructor, therefore, an instructional approach that guides learning”. The critical factor to active learning, especially in mathematics, is collaborative learner involvement which can assist the learner in improving their conceptions by using their peer explanations to solve problems (Webb et al., 2019). [...] Virtanen et al. (2017, p. 2) concur, citing that active learning is an “instructional method that engages learners and includes them as active participants in the learning process”. To enhance active learning, teachers need to guide learners to take responsibility for what they learn (Virtanen et al., 2017), particularly as active learning can improve learners’ attitude, understanding of the content (Mathias, 2014) and enhance the development of their mathematical skills. (Mahlambi, 2021, p. 473, 475).

The active learning conceptions comprise a constructivist vision with active student participation. In activities such as these, the student is not led to repeat the information provided by the teacher in a test, as is done in a traditional class, but he or she is invited to research the topic of the class by himself or herself, seeking concepts and information on that topic, develop them and explain them to the colleagues.

If colleagues do not understand, the student is challenged to explain the topic in a different way, making the student revisit the knowledge already acquired, reassess it and reconstruct a new argument that is more coherent or does not have logic errors. In case there are, the student responsible for explaining the task will be forced to question him or herself and re-evaluate the concepts. Thus, the goal is to create strategies to overcome the conceptual and epistemological difficulties manifested in the learning process.

Such activity, having so many layers, is one of the most powerful and efficient methods used in the teaching-learning process. Inverting the teacher–student role, and giving the student the opportunity to teach his or her classmates, enables the student to gain a greater understanding about the subject, since knowing how to explain a concept or topic in different ways shows that the student has truly studied and knows about the subject at hand (Srinath, 2014). It is important to support the students in the construction of a coherent knowledge and that they can actively participate in the recognition and construction of this knowledge “following the sequence: identification of the phenomenon, identification of the variables/elements involved, identification of interactions among them; search for regularities in the observed behaviors, conclusion on the concepts or law involved” (Bravo et al., 2022, p. 06, translated by the authors).

Thus, by placing students not as listeners, but as lecturers, debaters, monitors, the student almost completes the role of protagonist in the learning process. It is also understood that elaborating and conducting a workshop is not limited to explaining the class topic, but also to researching and elaborating didactic material, making the student-monitor role even more active in the studies, developing a sense of responsibility and motivation to learn and do a good job.

3 An Initiative that Aims at Gender Equity in STEM

The Accelerating Girls Project in Elementary School (MAF) is an extension project developed with female students from Elementary School Center 201 in Santa Maria, a public school located in the Federal District. In view of the low adherence of girls and women to STEM areas in higher education, which is related to the gender issue in education, the extension project acted in the planning, elaboration and execution of exact science

workshops with themes related to the school curriculum of the 9th grade of that elementary school using active learning methodologies in all activities. The project was conducted in 2021 and then due to the COVID-19 pandemic, took place remotely. Six female students were chosen by the school science teacher, who was a partner in the project, and the criteria used were based on their performance in science or their interest in participating in the project.

The direct work focused only on the female gender is based on studies that show that the group composed solely of women has more positive attitudes towards topics that are considered male-dominated (Cooper and Weaver, 2003)

The group that assists the students is made up of undergraduate students from the University of Brasília in the Statistics, Chemistry, Forestry Engineering, Mechanical Engineering and Electrical Engineering courses — they act as facilitators with the Elementary School students. The project also counts with the support of professors from the University of Brasília who work in engineering, education, psychology, sociology, design, and communication. They guide and supervise the activities developed. During the year, this team carried out workshops in which the main performers were the Elementary School (EF) students, who presented, based on their lesson plan, workshops to their colleagues in mixed classes, developing theoretical and practical aspects previously studied by the whole class.

The Accelerating Girls project in Elementary School was born as a segment of the Fast Girls project, which aims to encourage the entry of girls and women into STEM areas, being also developed with students from public schools, including High School ones. It is promoted due to the low permanence and interest of women in these areas.

According to Linda Gottfredson (1981), from the age of 6 to 8, children begin to form ideas about the influence of gender in relation to professions and this becomes evident when reaching adolescence, when abilities, values and interests based on childhood are used to make possible professional choices and roles to be taken. Several factors consolidate ideas on what would or would not be appropriate for a given gender, from stereotypes, self-esteem, expectations, gender roles to the absence of female role models (Munilla, 2018). This, when internalized, influences the vocational behavior of young people, limiting their achievements and aspirations (Betz & Hackett, 1981; Faria, Taveira, & Saavedra, 2008). Therefore, in order to promote gender equity and inclusion, it is necessary to act since basic education.

In this sense, the Accelerating Girls in Elementary School aims to foster interest and create a safe space for elementary school students, providing opportunities for the expression of creativity, logical reasoning and improving their interest in the areas of mathematics, science and technology. Thus, they are encouraged to face the likely difficulties related to the gender issue in their path, creating conditions so as not to interrupt this journey through educational practices which are sensitive to this problem.

3.1 Workshops Model and Methodology

Through active and collaborative learning models, development of practical activities and bringing scientific content closer to everyday life, workshops led by elementary school students were developed. The workshops followed the same structure, being divided into stages over five weeks: (1) Delimiting the themes of the workshop, and the beginning of the studies stage; (2) Designing the flipped classroom; (3) Slides preparation; (4) Experiment characterization. Preparation of quizzes and questionnaires; (5) Testing the workshop. After the stages had been performed, it was possible to present them to the target audience.

The workshops were planned according to the syllabus studied in the 9th year of Elementary School, covering topics such as matter and energy, covering areas of physics, biological sciences, mathematics, chemistry and others. Themes such as density, chemical reactions, waves and Newton's laws were the guiding principles in the four workshops held. Within them several aspects were discussed in a multidisciplinary way, contemplating both the theoretical and the practical parts of the deliberate areas. These various aspects can be observed in Table 1.

After having delimited the theme, a week was used for studies, carrying out research activities in books, websites, articles and searching for videos, images and various didactic resources to formulate ideas about the

chosen content. This step is essential for the delineation of the workshop's pillars, and it helps the elementary school monitors to remember and fix the content previously discussed in the classroom.

Perusall, a platform for inserting images, PDF and media files, hyperlinks and other resources, developed by educational researchers and behavioral and data scientists from Harvard University, was one of the resources connecting undergraduate monitors and elementary students because, in a versatile way, it was possible to highlight important parts of the texts, share new content, exchange comments and ask questions collectively, enabling an individual activity to be carried out in a collaborative way.

Based on the contents studied and the didactic resources that were grouped, a flipped classroom strategy was designed, preparing students for the contents that would be discussed later in the presentation. The flipped classroom has proven to be an important strategy for both preparing the elementary school monitors and delivering the workshop to the class. Wankat and Oreovicz (2015) defined the flipped classroom as a pedagogical approach that includes a three-step didactic sequence, pre-class, class, and post-class. In training the students to conduct the workshops, it is possible to distinguish the three stages: (i) previous studies on the subject; (ii) feedback and development of collaborative work; (iii) individual work.

Through videos, short texts, images and games, the students were expected to begin a brief study of the topic. The contents studied also contributed to the formulation of the presentation slides. These were developed from summaries written by the elementary students in their study phase, and included gifs, small texts, images and references. The last week execution of the proposed steps was related to the formulation and delimitation of experiments, quizzes and questionnaires.

Table 1. Workshops conducted and their specifications.

Workshop	Themes approached	Experiment(s)
Matter properties – Density	Concept of weight, mass, volume and density. Density calculation. Immiscible substances. Factors that can modify the density of a material. Relationship between temperature and density. Relationship between physical state of matter and its density.	Lava lamp
Chemical reactions	Meaning of chemical transformation. Signs of reactions occurring. How chemical reactions are written. Types of chemical transformations. Factors that prove the occurrence of a reaction.	Potassium permanganate solution, water oxygenated and manganese dioxide
Waves and wave phenomena	Definition of wave, amplitude, wavelength, period, speed and frequency of a wave. Wave classification. Direction of wave propagation and vibration. Examples of wave phenomena. Definition of sound waves and their properties.	Wave machine and experiment with sound waves
Newton's laws	Concept of kinematics and dynamics, and their differences. The history of Isaac Newton. Distinction of force and resultant force. Description of different types of force. Concept behind Newton's laws.	Experiment with coins (principle of inertia), experiment with eggs (law of inertia), experiment with displacement of a rubber (principle of dynamics) and experiment with balloons (principle of action and reaction)

The Elementary School students, after the steps outlined above, performed the presentation of the chosen theme. The class given was conducted as followed: theoretical presentation; resolution of doubts in relation to the theoretical part; quiz; experiment presentation; solving practical doubts.

The quizzes, which served as a way of evaluating the understanding of the workshops, were prepared by the elementary students. They included five to seven questions which were discussed in class after the theoretical presentation, in order to contemplate the main points that were exposed in the presentation.

Based on the fact that knowledge can only be developed in the individual's own action (Freire, 2001), the experiments were thought of as a way of correlating the contents taught with the knowledge and narratives that students observed in their daily lives, in order to make Physics and Chemistry more understandable and less abstract to students. These experiments were designed with accessible materials, made available to elementary school monitors by the guiding professors and purchased with resources offered by the Federal District Research Support Foundation (FAP-DF). All experiments were exposed to the class in order to highlight the materials needed for the elaboration and their step-by-step assembly. These could be replicated by the students in their homes.

Before the class presentation, the elementary students presented the complete workshop to the undergraduate monitors and coordinating professors, so that they could discuss aspects that could be improved and small adjustments could be made. That served as a rehearsal and the workshop improvement.

Questionnaires were prepared by the undergraduate monitors to assess the impact of the workshops on the classes where they were taught. They were sent after the end of the presentation. These involved questions including the flipped classroom, the experiment, and length of presentation, content presented, the quiz, the presenters' didactics, among others. The questionnaires contributed to changes throughout the workshops, making them adequate to the target audience. This moment was also important for their learning and autonomy in the process of designing and executing the workshops.

4 Results

The six female elementary school students who participated in the project during 2021 conducted four workshops as class monitors in a remote virtual environment for about 80 students, boys and girls in the ninth grade of a science class at Elementary School Center 201 in Santa Maria, on the outskirts of Brasília, Federal District. Figure 1 shows the cover of the material produced for the flipped classroom and screenshots of the presentation and the experiment performed by the elementary school monitors.

Figure 1. Workshop of Chemical Reactions: flipped classroom material; remote class presentation; and remote experiment.

To analyze the results obtained with the project, interviews were conducted with these six female students. The interview had 10 questions that addressed the thematic axes: (1) General aspects (issues related to STEM areas and active learning methodologies); (2) Adherence to the project; and (3) Encouraging protagonism.

When asked about the project's contribution to increasing their interest in STEM fields, all students answered affirmatively. One of the interviewees is considering studying aerospace engineering, while another reported an increased interest in robotics. It was also emphasized that, although they had not previously excelled in mathematics, participating in the project brought them closer to the STEM areas.

Regarding the small age difference between undergraduate and elementary school students, there was unanimity in highlighting the age range as a positive point, being interpreted as a contributing factor to the creation of a relaxed environment. When asked about the methods and strategies adopted, experiments and quizzes, these were positively evaluated, highlighting the playful and interactive nature of these proposals. The inverted classroom was also mentioned; they emphasized its important role in the study and individual preparation before the workshop with the undergraduate monitors.

One of the interviewees emphasized that the research activity helped thematic understanding in comparison with traditional learning methods. All of the interviewees evaluated the experiments as a facilitating strategy

for understanding the content. Such active methodology strategies, according to two of the interviewees, were responsible for their better performance in science assessments.

This effectiveness in performance on assessments changes how female students perceive themselves in the face of learning in STEM. The issue of vocation is called into question when girls realize that the problem is not an individual characteristic. The prejudices linked to gender begin to be addressed through the use of an active methodology that develops autonomy, interaction, and creativity.

Moving on to axis 2, about the questions referring to adherence to the project's gender proposal, when asked about the motivations needed to continue in the project, one of the answers was "I liked it a lot because there were only girls". One of the students commented that being with her classmates was a motivational factor to continue doing the workshops.

For those who left or thought of leaving the project early, they were asked to explain their motivations. One of the students explained that the pandemic and, possibly, remote learning, left her demotivated and, for this reason, she thought of leaving the project, but that after talking to one of the group members she decided to stay. This student participated in all four workshops and reiterated that, despite not being the central incentive, the CNPq scholarship she received encouraged her to keep going to the meetings.

All students confirmed their interest in participating in future project actions. In fact, four of them have already started to participate in the Fast Girls project after entering high school. One of the students said that the project during the pandemic was an encouraging factor for her, as it fostered interaction with other classmates, which was hindered by physical isolation during the pandemic.

In axis 3, which dealt with the students' protagonism in the project, all of them answered that they had autonomy to decide the themes of the workshops and discuss the strategies used, although one of the students commented that not all of them used this autonomy to give their opinion on the methods and strategies used in the workshops.

Finally, when asked about the benefits of having participated in the project and what they learned in the process that they would take back to high school, the answers ranged from improved teamwork dynamics to improved public speaking and presentation skills.

In this perspective, when acting as monitors, the elementary school students felt protagonists in the presentations and in carrying out the experiments, and realized greater resourcefulness, greater curiosity in the classroom and greater ability to understand and correlate content. Through the methods and strategies used and the production of materials based on the theories studied in class, the students were able to consolidate their knowledge and instigate classmates to think critically. Understanding that active learning requires questioning, problematization, and the sensorial and emotional experience of knowledge (Oliveira, 2006), which are not such characteristics explored in the standard learning process in which students absorb knowledge in a passive way (Leão, 1999). As we could see from the reports, the project correlated the contents to the students' reality, encouraging them to observe and question phenomena, allowed the appropriation of methodological tools, of experiences in the construction of scientific knowledge and its articulation with everyday life, as well as developing skills in organizing, planning, and executing the workshops.

5 Concluding Remarks

The selected students are a vulnerable group - taking into account monetary parameters, housing region and gender and race identification - in this sense, this is a valuable project in the socioeconomic sphere, being in line with what is advocated by Adams, Gupta and Cotumaccio (2014), who argue that science programs, outside the school, help in the trajectory of young people in the scientific world, especially girls from underrepresented groups in this area. Thus, it is generalized that, although it brings elements that are similar to successful initiatives regarding the encouragement of girls and women in STEM areas, because it is a project still in its infancy, the process of interest needs to be maintained and deepened so that it can introduce relevant changes that enable the promotion of the advancement of women that is necessary in the scientific and technological field, as well as in educational institutions.

The 2030 Agenda, together with UNESCO, has placed STEM education as one of the pillars for achieving this goal. In this sense, actions to encourage girls to engage in Science, Engineering, Technology and Mathematics developed while still at school age proved to be positive. In light of this, the project Accelerating Girls in Elementary School, with the use of Active Learning, developed its activities in order to encourage girls and women in the areas of STEM, encouraging the permanence of undergraduates in the areas and providing a more personal and active initiation of Elementary School students with Exact Sciences. In view of what has been exposed, the results obtained so far have shown to be promising, since even those students who had no initial interest in STEM remained motivated and participatory during the activities. Currently, the Accelerating Girls in Elementary School project aims to migrate to the face-to-face format without any loss in the quality of the workshops, evasion of monitors and losses of its central idea.

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